

A New Method of Estimating Arsenic in Organo-arsenic Derivatives. Part I.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The application of organic derivatives of arsenic as drugs, has brought into prominence the problem of estimating the metalloid, when directly combined with carbon. A survey of the references given in the foot-note, will clearly explain the fact that each author by adopting a new method or some modifications of the older ones aimed at getting an inorganic derivative of arsenic either by dry or moist combustion of the organic compound, the arsenic being subsequently estimated either gravimetrically or volumetrically.

A method of estimating arsenic in organic tissues, devised by Norton and Koch (*loc. cit.*) has been successfully utilised in the estimation of the metalloid in its organic derivatives by Ewins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1356). The method has its universal application but suffers from the main drawback that the end point is never sharp and that the experiment is attended with vigorous frothing at the outset which can be controlled only with difficulty.

In course of some experiments on the problem of introducing pentavalent arsenic into therapeutically active organic compounds, the author's attention was drawn to the fact that with the exception of a very few, majority of the organo-arsenic acids are soluble in hydrochloric acid. Anticipating that the arsenic, which is in its highest state of oxidation in such compounds, should liberate an equivalent amount of iodine in presence of hydrochloric acid from a solution of potassium iodide, pure phenylarsinic acid was treated in a similar

La Coste and Michaelis, *Annalen*, 1880, 201, 224; Gooch and Browning, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1890, iii, 11, 66; Little, Cahen and Morgan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1478; Pringsheim, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 31, 336; Mouthule, *Ann. chim. Anal.*, 1904, 9, 308; Morgan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1001; Norton and Koch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 1247; Martindale, *Extra Pharmacopoeia*, 1915, 11, 27; Kircher and Rupert, *Ber. (Deut. Pharm. Ges.)*, 1920, 30, 419, 421; Newbery, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1925, 127, 1751; R Stollé and O Fechtig, *Ber. Deut. Pharm. Ges.*, 1923, 33, 59; Kolthoff, *Z. Annal. Chem* 1923, 62, 137, 38.

way. The analytical results obtained proved the correctness of the assumption. This gave a clue to an easier way of estimating the pentavalent arsenic in organo-arsenic acids as the liberated iodine may easily be titrated by means of sodium thiosulphate. The method is very rapid (from fifteen to twenty minutes for the estimation) and gave accurate results with the compounds enumerated below. A few of the typical organo-arsenic derivatives belonging to different groups have been examined. The advantages of the method are that it requires only a very small quantity (from ten to fifteen mg.) of the substance and requires only simplest apparatus and materials. Organo arsenic acids that are insoluble in hydrochloric acid are, first of all, brought into solution by heating with glacial acetic acid and then treated with hydrochloric acid and potassium iodide solution. A compound of this type *viz.*, naphthylarsinic acid (Hill and Balls. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 2051) has been tried with success.

The following table summarises the experimental results of the present investigations.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Substance.	Quantity.	Arsenic content.	
		Found.	Calc.
Ethylarsinic acid	·0286 g.	48·28	48·7 per cent.
	·0170	48·19	
Phenylarsinic acid	·0178	37·2	37·1
	·0146	37·1	
	·0201	37·09	
Benzylarsinic acid	·0218	34·69	34·7
	·0252	34·78	
Naphthylarsinic acid	·0126	29·1	29·7
	·0101	29·08	
Triconarylarinic oxide	·0225	14·16	14·2
	·0199	14·09	
7-Methylcoumarin-6-arsinic acid	·0116	26·1	26·4
	·0124	26·08	
4:7-Dimethylcoumarin-6-arsinic acid	·0110	25·25	25·3
	·0221	25·3	
Naphthacoumarin-6-arsinic acid	·0204	23·25	23·4
	·0199	23·3	
4-Methylnaphthacoumarin-6-arsinic acid	·0193	22·45	22·4
	·0265	22·5	

Procedure—A small quantity of the substance (0.01 to 0.02 g.) was weighed out accurately in a conical flask of about 300 c. c. capacity. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c. *d* 1.19) was run in and the whole heated on a water-bath for five minutes. In case an uniform solution is not obtained, the mixture should be heated by direct flame. The solution was cooled to the room temperature and glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.) were then added. In a separate beaker potassium iodide (4 g.) dissolved in water (10 c.c.) was added to the acid solution. The solution assumed a brown or yellow coloration due to the liberation of free iodine. The walls of the flask were then washed with a little water and the liberated iodine titrated against *N*/20 sodium thiosulphate solution. Towards the end of the titration 2 c.c. of a one per cent. solution of starch was added and the titration continued to the end. After the point at which the blue coloration, due to free iodine and starch, faded away which however was not the exact end point, the thiosulphate solution was carefully added drop by drop with constant stirring till the original colour of the solution of the substance in hydrochloric acid was attained.

From the amount of thiosulphate solution required, the percentage of arsenic present is easily calculated. One c.c. of *N*/20 thiosulphate solution \equiv 0.000375 g. of arsenic.

Experiments with other derivatives of arsenic, in the tri-valent state, are in progress.

In conclusion I wish to express my gratitude to Dr. M. Goswami, for his kind interest and valuable suggestions in this investigation.

APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received February 3, 1932.

